

**STRUCTURE OF THE GERBERIL *RHOMBOMYS OPIMUS* (LICHT, 1823) (RODENT)
POPULATIONS IN THE WESTERN PART OF THE BETPAKDALA DESERT**

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Introduction

The study of rodents in the Betpakdala desert was carried out in the 30-60s. XX century [1-8]. After the discovery in 1983 in the northwest of the desert of the plague pathogen in rodent settlements [9], a detailed study of the structure of settlements of the most widespread species began. Subsequently, epizootics among rodents were often found in the western, central and eastern parts of the desert, so this territory was identified as a new independent (autonomous) Betpakdala natural plague focus. The study of the great gerbil and other rodents in the western part of the Betpakdala desert, since the late 70s, has been successfully continued. Most of the studies were devoted to the issues of seasonal changes in the abundance of the great gerbil as the main carrier of plague in the Central Asian desert focus and the influence of anthropogenic and natural factors on the number and density of its population [10–14]. Of no small importance are the issues of the rate of recovery of the abundance of this rodent after its extinction over large areas, as well as the landscape confinement to desert territories [15–17].

Originally, the Betpakdala desert was used as a seasonal pasture by livestock breeders to the south, in the Moynkum desert and along the foothill plains. Cattle driving routes passed through Betpakdala, along which cattle were driven north in spring to Saryarka, south of the Kazakh uplands, and in autumn back to Moynkum. Thanks to millions of herds of saiga, in the past, a hunting economy developed here.

Since the 70s of the last century, uranium mining, exploration of gas deposits and other minerals began in the Betpakdala desert. Industrial development was accompanied by anthropogenic changes in natural landscapes, which led to a change and the emergence of new rodent settlements. This was especially reflected in the populations of the great gerbil [18].

Unfortunately, to date, data on the settlements of the great gerbil on a cartographic basis in Betpakdala are not enough, and due to a number of reasons, the distribution of the great gerbil in the territory is devoid of detail [4, 9, 14, 19]. Therefore, our task was to specify all known gerbil settlements by 2022 with a brief description of them within the western part of the Betpakdala desert.

Materials and methods

The materials are based on accumulated long-term observations in the process of epizootological examination within the Turkestan region (Sozak region) and Ulytau region (Ulytau region). The survey area in the south runs along the Shu River (44°45'–45°00' N), in the north to the Zhideli sands (47°15' N). The length was about 300 km. In the west, the border is the Sarysu River (67°10' E), in the east, the survey area reached the border with the Zhambyl region (69°30' E), which was about 200 km from west to east. The survey area was more than 50 thousand km².

Where there are high-density colonies of great gerbil, they were directly captured for laboratory research between 1983 and 2021 with some interruptions. In areas with low density, settlements were studied by reconnaissance trips. More than 20 trips were made, the total length of which was more than 30 thousand km.

Results and discussions

Due to the heterogeneity of landscapes, vegetation, rodent settlements, as well as the peculiarities of the epizootic plague process, the territory of the western part of Betpakdala, based on long-term observations, was divided into 3 landscape epizootological regions (LER): Sholakespin, Western Betpakdala and Karakoyyn [20]. In the study area, we have identified 4 main types of colonies of the great gerbil: diffuse, ribbon, island and solitary. Figure 1 shows a detailed diagram of the colonies of the great gerbil.

Figure 1 - Map-scheme of the settlements of the great gerbil

The following is a description of the colonies of the great gerbil within each LER.

Sholakespinskiy LER (1). Administratively, this is the Sozak district of the Turkestan region. From the south, this area borders on the river Shu, in the north the border runs along $45^{\circ}15' N.$, in the west along the river. Sarysu, in the east - in the area of the artesian well Sholakespe. The main landscape is represented by a sandy hilly plain with thickets of saxaul (*Haloxylon*). There are large takyr and solonchaks (Askazansor,

Kakpansor, etc.) around which saltworts grow. Wormwood-ephemeral plant associations are found throughout the territory. In this area, the diffuse type of settlements of the great gerbil prevails with a density of colonies from 150 to 250 per $1 km^2$. The number of animals ranges from 50 to 2000 or more per $1 km^2$. The density of colonies and the number of gerbils are noticeably higher along salt marshes. Here the number of rodents is more stable for a number of years.

In the specified area there is a working settlement of Taikonyr and large uranium mining enterprises -

LLP SP "Inkai 1" and "Inkai 2" with their own infrastructure, which employ about 800 employees. Places where there are artesian wells or wells are used by livestock breeders as seasonal sites for livestock.

LER Western Betpakdala (2). Administratively, the district is located in the Sozak district of the Turkestan region. This area is located between two other LERs, Sholakepinsky and Karakoyinsky. In the south, the district borders on the Sholakespin LER and the Shu River, in the north, the border runs along a ledge (chink), which creates a drop from the plateau to the plain by 10–45 meters. In the west, its border is the Sarysu River, and in the east, the region has no clear geographical boundaries. Conventionally, it passes through the island settlements of the great gerbil 69°30' E.

The main part of the region is located on a plateau, which consists of gravel-argillaceous plains with small ridges. The vegetation is represented by thickets of boyalych (*Salsola*) and sagebrush-ebelek associations. Saxaul forests are found only in the Inkuduk tract.

A large settlement of the great gerbil is located in the Inkuduk tract (the area of the Zhalpak deposit), where it is represented in a diffuse form (Fig. 2A). (Figures 2-3 are based on images from the Google Earth Pro application in the public domain). The white spots in the figure are colonies of the great gerbil. The density of colonies varies from 150 to 250 colonies, and in some places reaches 300 colonies per 1 km². Another settlement, but of an island type, is located in the southeast of the described territory (Fig. 2B). Groups of colonies are outlined. Here the density varies from 50 to 200 colonies per 1 km². Tape settlements of the great gerbil run along the road from Zhuantobe village to Kyzemshek village and further to the turn to the Zhalpak deposit. They are found in areas along the Pavlodar-Shymkent oil pipeline, railway and highways, etc. The gerbil actively populates the emerging new

roads, embankments, various pipelines, which everywhere accompany the construction of new drilling sites and mining enterprises [17]. Even with the reconstruction of roads, colonies destroyed by heavy road equipment reappear within 2-3 years, and after a while there are already solid colonies, barely distinguishable only by the ecological center. The density in tape settlements reaches 8 or more colonies per 1 ha. On the territory of the LER there are still single colonies. They are so rare that only 1-2 colonies can be found at a distance of 5-7 km. But, as a rule, such colonies are large, 25-30 m in diameter, with a good ecological center, on which at least 5-10, and sometimes more than 15 animals live. It is extremely difficult to determine the density of colonies in such settlements.

Karakoin LER (3). Administratively, this district is located on the territory of the Ulytau district of the Ulytau region. In the south, the border runs along a steep ledge (chink) with a height difference of 10 to 45 meters. The northern boundary runs along the northern edge of the Zhetykonyrsky sands (47°15' N), but still requires further clarification. In the west, the border is the river. Sarysu. In the east, the boundary of the area runs approximately along the eastern settlements of the great gerbil (69° 15' E), but also requires clarification. In this LER, plains alternate with sand massifs: Semenkum, Katynkum, Sasykshengel, Karakoin, Zhetykonyr, Sarysu Moiynkum. On clay plains, vegetation is represented by sagebrush-ebelek-ephemeral associations, and boylychevy thickets. In areas with takyr, many saltworts (*Salsola*) and saltworts (*Salicornia*) grow. The sand massifs are covered with ephemera, wormwood and zhuzgun (*Calligonum*). Very rich vegetation along the edge of the sands, consisting of zhuzgun, chia (*Achnatherum*) and cereals. In the north of the study area, feather grass is found in some places - an element of the steppes.

A - Diffuse settlement; B - Island settlements.
Fig. 2 - Types of settlements of the great gerbil in Western Betpakdala

Settlements of the great gerbil in the indicated area were discovered and studied by us relatively recently since 2014.

Greater gerbil from the cliff to the north occurs in the form of rather large settlements up to 46°20' N. Further to the north, it lives along the edge of the sands in the form of ribbon settlements 3-4 km wide or patches

of 30-40 colonies, up to 100 hectares in area. A large diffuse sporadic settlement (up to 1200 km²) is located east of the Karakoin Sands, between 46°17' and 46°40' N. and stretches to the east for 25-30 km. The landscape is a sandy hilly plain, the vegetation is a sagebrush-ebel association with rare shrubs of undersized saxaul. The terrain is interspersed with lowlands with takyr, thickets of chiy and reeds (*Phragmites*). The density of colonies ranges from 180 to 350 per km². The remaining sporadic settlements of the gerbil are located in small patches (up to 500 ha) around salt marshes, in the places of old livestock breeders' camps, along large ravines and gullies. On clay soils, north of the Tamgaly tract, the density of colonies is low, no more than 200 per km². In places of high standing of groundwater, single colonies are found on small hills.

Tape settlements of the great gerbil are located along the Pavlodar-Shymkent oil pipeline, where the density of colonies reaches 450 per km², and Kumkol-Karakoin, the density of colonies is up to 800 per 1 km². During the years of high habitation of colonies, there is

a very high abundance here, more than 4000 animals per km². Another belt settlement is located along the highway that goes to the mines of the Zhaman-Aibat deposit. Here there are small, up to 3 km long areas inhabited by a large gerbil with a density of up to 3.5 colonies per 1 ha. Another belt settlement is located along the railway, which also goes from Zhezkazgan to the Zhaman-Aibat mines. The colonies are located in separate areas along the embankment and stretch to the sandy massif. The last colonies along the road embankment were found at 47°02'/68°42'. Further, the road is laid through the sands and stretches to the northwest, but we did not find a large gerbil there. Probably sandy soil is not suitable for burrow construction.

The northernmost colony of the great gerbil was found on the outskirts of the Zhetykonyr sands at 47°04'/68°35'. The gerbil will probably settle to the north, but in anthropogenic landscapes. Belt colonies of sand lance are located along the roads leading to the Zhaman-Aibat deposit (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Northernmost colony groups of the great gerbil in western Betpakdala

The greater gerbil was not found in the central part of the sand massifs. Possibly, the soil for the construction of burrows is not suitable here: loose sand, loosely fixed by vegetation. Observations that the great sand lance rarely inhabits or generally avoids large hilly ridge sands near the northern boundary of the range are also found in other studies [21–22].

The first observations of the movement of the great gerbil to the north were noted already in the middle of the last century. Its northernmost settlements in western Betpakdala are indicated in the vicinity of the Taban well (46°10'-46°15'N) [4]. Subsequently, the place of discovery of settlements of the great gerbil was noted on the southern margin of the Semenkum sands (46°15'-46°20'N), further in the western part of Betpakdala, the northern boundary corresponds to 46°20'-46°25'. However, it was noted that the northern limit of the range of the gerbil in Betpakdala has not yet been clearly established [19]. On the opposite side,

closer to the floodplain of the Sarysu River, the settlements of the great gerbil formed a “ledge” to the north, where rodents were found much further north than in Betpakdala, in the area of the Kyzyl-Kak, the Baska-saun tract (47°05'N) [23]. But in modern studies, the northern boundary of the great gerbil along the right bank of the Sarysu River is already indicated much further south [24].

It is difficult to determine the period of time during which the great gerbil spread 80-90 km northward, especially in relation to diffuse and sporadic settlements. Probably, their appearance is associated with the general aridization of the climate and the advance of deserts to the north, as well as human activity [25]. On the other hand, ribbon settlements arose 2–3 years after the construction of a road or the laying of an oil pipeline, as happened in the southern part of Betpakdala [17]. Thus, the construction of the Pavlodar-Shymkent oil pipeline began in the early 1980s. The road from the Zhaman-Aibat field was built in 2001-2004, and the

railway in 2004-2006. It should be noted that during the construction period of the road (2003-2006), large-scale exploration work was carried out in the area associated with violation of the integrity of the soil, to which the gerbil quickly reacts, populating artificial embankments, ditches, and dumps. In the spring of 2014, when we carried out the first surveys, belt colonies of the great gerbil were already recorded along the embankment of the highway.

Our observations over a number of years have shown the instability of small gerbil populations in the northern part of Betpakdala. In years with good weather and food conditions, with a stable population, these settlements are easy to spot. Some groups of burrows merge, forming single, similar to diffuse settlements. During the period of decline in numbers, the main part of the colonies remains uninhabited, and sometimes simply - in the form of spots in the landscape. Residential colonies form small groups with significant gaps between them. As early as the 1970s, the extinction of the great gerbil along the northern borders of Betpakdala in dry years was noted [5]. At the border of the range, gerbil settlements look like lace, populating only suitable areas. Probably, the unfavorable climatic conditions for gerbils in the northern subzone of the desert are abundant precipitation in winter and high humidity in burrows [26, 27]. It is known that the determining reasons for the movement of the great gerbil to the north are a clearly noticeable warming, accompanied by no less pronounced aridization of the climate [28].

In the conditions of the northern part of Betpakdala in winter, the height of the snow cover in some places reaches 20-40 cm. Thaws at the end of winter and early spring are also characteristic of Betpakdala, which are accompanied by a sharp melting of snow, and then frosts again. This causes flooding of burrows and the death of their hosts, especially in landscape depressions with dense ground [16]. Therefore, in the north of Betpakdala, only banded gerbil colonies are the most stable. The habitability of holes in them, even in the most unfavorable years, does not fall below 40-50%. Previously, it was noted that the belt settlements of gerbils in the southern part of Betpakdala and Moyinkum are stations for experiencing adverse conditions and contribute to the rapid spread of plague epizootics among rodents [17]. Therefore, in the conditions of Betpakdala, it is important to conduct a constant epidemiological examination for preventive purposes.

Findings

As a result of many years of studying the rodents of the western Betpakdala, settlements of the great gerbil were mapped.

In connection with the industrial development of the desert, accompanied by anthropogenic changes in natural landscapes, new settlements of the great gerbil appear.

Due to the impact of anthropogenic natural factors, the gerbil settled 80-90 km north of the previously known boundaries.

Knowledge of the characteristics of the distribution of the great gerbil in Betpakdala is of both scientific and practical importance for the necessary preventive anti-epidemic measures.

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References:

1. Kashkarov D.N. Zoological sketch of the eastern part of the Betpak-Dala desert // Proceedings of CASU. Ser. 8-a. Zoology. release 20. Tashkent, 1935, 30 p.
2. Beloslyudov B.A. Mammals of the Betpak-Dala desert // news of the AS Kaz. SSR. Ser. Zool. - 1948, - No. 63. - release 8. - pp. 51-78.
3. Sludsky A.A., Ismagilov M.I. Features of the geographical distribution of rodents in the Betpak-Dala desert and its significance for the natural focality of especially dangerous infections // Scientific conference on natural focality and epidemiology of especially dangerous diseases. Thesis of the report - Saratov, 1957. - pp. 362-364..
4. Ismagilov M.I. Ecology of rodents in Betpak-Dala and Southern Balkhash region. - Alma-Ata, 1961. - 368 p.
5. Ismagilov M.I. The boundaries of the ranges of rodents (Rodentia) of Central Kazakhstan // Teriology. - Novosibirsk: Science, 1974. - N. 2.- pp. 130-149.
6. Kasatkin B.M. Greater gerbil in the Balkhash region and the fight against it // Abstract of the dissertation. ... candidate of biological sciences. - Alma-Ata, 1954. - 18 p.
7. Kasatkin B.M. (The structure of the northern part of the range of the great gerbil and the problems of healing this part of the natural plague focus // Material for the conference on land zoogeography. Abstracts of reports - Alma-Ata, 1960. - pp. 60-61.
8. Bondar E.P. Materials on mammals of the Betpak-Dala desert and the southern part of the Kazakh highlands // Proceedings of the Central Asian Anti-Plague Institute. - 1956. - release 3. - pp. 107-121.
9. Sagymbekov U.A. Natural foci of plague in the northern subzone of the deserts of the Republic of Kazakhstan (Moyinkum, Saksauldala, Betpakdala) // Abstract of the dissertation of a doctor of medical sciences. - Almaty, 1995. - 50 p.
10. Rapoport L.P., Balabas N.G. On the question of seasonal changes in the number of great gerbils. // Quarantine and zoonotic infections in Kazakhstan. - Almaty, 2004 - No. 1 (9). - pp.106-109.
11. Rapoport L.P., Rakhimov K.R. Influence of anthropogenic factors on population density of the great gerbil and manifestations of plague in the deserts of the South // Quarantine and zoonotic infections in Kazakhstan. - Almaty, 2006. - No. 1-2 (13-14). - pp.193-194

12. Rapoport L.P. On the question of the rate of restoration of the population of the great gerbil (*Rhombomys opimus* Licht.) after its extinction over large areas. // Quarantine and zoonotic infections in Kazakhstan. - Almaty, 2007. - No. 1-2 (15-16), - pp. 118-120.
13. Kulemin M.V., Rapoport L.P., Putyatin V.V., Nuriev Kh.Kh., Sazhnev Yu.S., Balabas N.G. Influence of the drought of 2004-2006 on the number of main carriers and carriers of plague and the intensity of the epizootic process in the deserts of South Kazakhstan // Quarantine and zoonotic infections in Kazakhstan. - Almaty, 2008. - No. 1-2 (17-18). - pp. 75-80.
14. Sazhnev Yu.S., Rapoport L.P., Putyatin V.V. Materials on the landscape confinement of gerbil settlements in Western Betpakdala. // Quarantine and zoonotic infections in Kazakhstan. - Almaty, 2008. - No. 1-2 (17-18). - pp. 118-120.
15. Rapoport L.P. Biocenotic relationships of rodents in the deserts of Southern Kazakhstan and their role in the natural foci of human transmissible diseases // Quarantine and zoonotic infections in Kazakhstan. - Almaty, 2013 - No. 2 (28). - pp.31-35.
16. Kulemin M.V., Rapoport L.P., Sazhnev Yu.S., Shokputov T.M., Vasilenko A.V., Sailaubekuly R. Influence of the abnormally cold winter of 2011-2012. on the number of main carriers and vectors of plague and the intensity of the epizootic process in the deserts of South Kazakhstan. // Quarantine and zoonotic infections in Kazakhstan. - Almaty, 2014 - No. 2 (30). - pp. 44-48.
17. Sazhnev Yu.S., Kulemin M.V., Rapoport L.P., Sailaubekuly R., Rakhimov K.R. Influence of industrial development of the deserts of Southern Kazakhstan on the rodent fauna of natural foci of human transmissible diseases // Quarantine and zoonotic infections in Kazakhstan. - Almaty, 2013. - No. 2 (28). - pp. 37-41.
18. Sazhnev Yu.S., Rapoport L.P., Kulemin M.V., Abdukarimov N.A. On the relationship of rodent settlements with settlements in the Karakoyun landscape epizootological region (Western Betpakdala, Karaganda region) // Quarantine and zoonotic infections in Kazakhstan. - Almaty, 2016 - No. 1. - pp. 90-91.
19. Dubrovsky Yu.A., Burdelov A.S., Zhernovov I.V., Korinfsky A.N., Mitropolsky O.V., Rapoport L.P. Mapping the range of the great gerbil in Central Asia and Kazakhstan using the degree field method. // Modern problems of zoogeography. Moscow, 1980. - pp. 167-180.
20. Sazhnev Yu.S., Rapoport L.P., Kulemin M.V., Sailaubekuly R. Materials on landscape epizootological zoning of the western part of the Betpakdala autonomous plague focus // Quarantine and zoonotic infections in Kazakhstan. - Almaty, 2018. - No. 1-2 (36-37). - pp. 31-38.
21. Varshavsky S.N., Shilov M.N. Ecological and geographical features of the distribution and territorial distribution of the great gerbil in the Northern Aral Sea // Proceedings of the Central Asian Anti-Plague Institute, 1956. release 3. pp. 3-28
22. Burdelov A.S. Some features of the biotopic distribution of the great gerbil and its microstructure // Material of the VIII scientific conference of the anti-plague institution of Central Asia and Kazakhstan - Alma-Ata, 1974. - pp. 232-234.
23. Shilov M.N., Zhubanazarov I.Zh., Gulyaevskaya N.S., Li A.S., Misalaeva O.S., Aitkaliev B.A., Kartushin E.P., Koshenov U.A. Expansion of the ranges of plague carriers in the Trans-Aral region and urgent tasks of the Aralomorsk anti-plague station in the field of plague prevention // Abstracts of the report of the All-Union Conference "State and prospects for plague prevention". Saratov, 1978.- pp.126-129.
24. Matzhanova A.M., Moldabekov B.K., Iskakov B.G., Dosaev S.B., Zhangabylov N.M., Duisenova M.E. The northern border of the distribution range of the great gerbil in the zone of activity of the Kyzylorda ES.// Quarantine and zoonotic infections in Kazakhstan. Almaty, 2017. release. 1-2 (34-35). pp. 48-51.
25. Burdelov A.S. Human activity and the great gerbil // Proceedings of the VIII scientific conference of the anti-plague institution of Central Asia and Kazakhstan. - Alma-Ata, 1974. - 33. 234-237.
26. Burdelov A.S. The range of the great gerbil and its macrostructure. // Ecology and medical significance of gerbils of the fauna of the USSR. (Material of the All-Union Conference Ashgabat, 1977). Moscow, 1977. - pp. 63-66.
27. Shubin I.G. On the factors that determine the northern limits of the distribution of gerbils // Abstracts of reports. II All-Union Conference. on ecology and honey. importance of gerbils, the most important rodents of the arid zone. Alma-Ata, August 1981. Moscow, 1981.- pp.86-87.
28. Burdelov L.A., Dubyansky V.M., Meka-Mechenko V.G., Semenko O.V., Sadovskaya V.P. On the reasons for recent expansion of the range of the great gerbil (*Rhombomys opimus* Licht.) in Kazakhstan and neighboring countries: Mater. International scientific and practical. conf., consec. To the 100th anniversary of the birth of the founder of the Kazakh schools of theriology and hunting science, laureate of the state. prizes of the USSR and KazSSR, corresponding member. Academy of Sciences of the Kazakh SSR A. A. Sludsky (Almaty, March 1-2, 2012). - Almaty, 2012. - pp. 69-73.